

EFFECT OF REFRACTIVE ERROR AMONG SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS

Dr. Goutam Datta¹; Pooja Mandal²; Satarupa Mohanta³;

¹Associate Professor, Department of Optometry, Tripura Instituted of Paramedical Sciences

²Assistant Professor, Department of Optometry, Tripura Instituted of Paramedical Sciences

³2nd Semester PG Students, Department of Optometry, Tripura Instituted of Paramedical Sciences

ABSTRACT

BACKGROUND: A survey was done to identify if there is any relevance of effect of refractive error of eye. The study was done in the capital city AGARTALA of TRIPURA.

AIM: To know the effects of refractive error among secondary school students.

OBJECTIVES: Refractive errors are a type of vision problem that makes it hard to see clearly. They happen when the shape of your eye keeps light from focusing correctly on your retina.

MATERIAL AND METHODS: A Questionnaire based survey along with eye examination was done in the study, where 162 subjects were selected from the college campus of Tripura Institute of Paramedical Sciences, from October 2023 to February 2024.

INCLUSION CRITERIA: On the basis of demography and standard of study, the result for normal and complications have been identified.

RESULTS: In this study total 162 secondary school students were randomly selected. A questionnaires sheet was supplied to different school students of Agartala, which was included the visual performance, clinical examination, where 91 (56.17%) were girls and 71 (43.83%) were boys. It was also found that, due to refractive errors students were reducing their study time, that's directly hampered their study life. So, early detection or refractive errors correction is the most essentials for secondary school students.

DISCUSSION: In this study, we also found that the complications like headache and blurring of vision due to refractive error of study among school student, effect of refractive error is more in female students than male students.

CONCLUSION: A proper eye check-up is very important, at least once in a month to be aware of the leading symptoms and as required proper precautions must be taken especially while studying in an efficient manner.

KEYWORDS: *Headache, blurred vision, double vision, heaviness of eyelid, secondary school students, refractive errors,*

INTRODUCTION

Refractive errors are the second leading causes of blindness in India. Refractive errors are a type of vision problem that makes it hard to see clearly. They happen when the shape of eye keeps light from focusing correctly on the retina. Refractive errors are the most common type of vision problem. There are 4 common types of refractive errors: near-sightedness(myopia): makes far away objects look blurry; far-sightedness(hypermetropia): makes nearby objects look blurry; Astigmatism: can make far-away and nearby object look blurry or distorted; Presbyopia: makes it hard for middle aged and older adults (age above 40 year's) to see things up close.

Emmetropia: Emmetropia can be detained as a state of refraction where in the parallel rays of light coming from infinity are focused at the sensitive layer of retina with the accommodation being at rest.

Ametropia: Ametropia is defined as a state of refractive where in the parallel rays of light coming from infinity (when accommodation at rest) are focused either in front or behind the sensitive layer of retina, in one or both the meridian.

Ametropia include the following: Myopia; Hypermetropia; Astigmatism.

Myopia (near-sightedness): myopia or short sightedness is a type of refractive error in which parallel rays of light coming from infinity are focused in front of the retina when accommodation is at rest.

Hypermetropia(farsightedness): hypermetropia refers to the refractive state of the eye where in parallel rays of the coming from infinity are focusing behind the retina with accommodation being at the rest. Thus, the posterior focal point is behind the retina, which therefore, receives a blurry image.

Astigmatism: astigmatism is a type of refractive error where in the refraction varies in different meridian. Consequently, the rays of light entering the eye cannot converge to a point focus but from focal lines. Broadly, there are two types of astigmatism: regular astigmatism; irregular astigmatism.

This problem occurs when the shape or condition of the cornea – or the shape of cornea – or the shape of the eye ball, – results in an in accurate focusing of the light passing into the eye. Myopia usually results from the eye being too long or oval shaped rather than round. Farsightedness happens when the eyeball grows too short from front to back, or the cornea or lens. Astigmatism happens when the cornea or lens has a different shape than normal. The shape makes light bend differently as it enters in the eye, causing a refractive error.

Presbyopia: presbyopia is not an error of refraction but a condition of physiological insufficiency of accommodation due to reduced amplitude of accommodation, leading to a progressive fall in near vision. This condition of failing near vision due to age related decrease in the amplitude of accommodation or increases in punctum proximate is called presbyopia. It is a physiological disorder that affects everyone during the natural aging process. The most common systems of presbyopia occur around age of 40 years for most people, The symptoms of presbyopia typically involve a gradual deterioration in ability to read or do work up close.

Refractive error causes different types of problem in secondary school students because school students require the use of digital device like mobile, laptop, many types of instruments, practical and lot of study, because of that, the students get headache, eye pain or eyestrain.

Refractive errors constitute a proportion of any eye OPD in India. Refractive errors are considered in impairment public health problems affecting people all over the world. Generally, the reports about the link between factors associated with education and refractive errors among school levels imposed major consequence or public health. Refractive errors can have many issues including educational loss, economic issues low productivity and impaired quality of life. The available literature identities that a significant member of school student is suffering from refractive errors.

Refractive error occurs when the eye is unable to bend and focus light appropriately onto the retina. Refractive errors happens when the shape of the eye keeps light from focusing correctly on the retina. Each type of refractive error is different, but they all make it hard to see clearly. Such as: vision may become blurry; haziness and double vision; other common symptoms include headache as a result of eyestrain or difficulty reading; seeing a glare or hole around bright lights; trouble focusing when reading or looking at a computer. In children refractive error may affects a child's reading level and a negative impact on overall learning. Problems with refractive errors can be subtle at first as the condition may not notice these symptoms until they are pronounced or start affecting your daily life. Symptoms can include: trouble focusing when reading or looking at a computer. In this study we are choosing those students, who are age limit 14 – 16 years of life. Before 40 years of life no students were found under this age group. That's why, we were excluded the presbyopia. We only included myopic patient and hypermetropic patient and astigmatic patients in this study.

METHODOLOGY

Aim of the Study: The aim of the study could be to investigate the impact of refractive errors on the school students, and to determine how refractive error hamper the study of school students.

Study of the Area: This study was conducted in different secondary schools of Tripura, Agartala west Tripura. In this study young school students with an age range of 14 to 16 years have been taken. Collect academic performance data and compare it between students with or without refractive error. Conduct longitudinal studies to tract changes in refractive error prevalence and academic performance overtime. This can provide insights into the progression of visual issues and their impact on students throughout their school year.

Time Period: The study was completed from October 2023 to February 2024. Male and Female both patients were present in this study.

Method and Materials:

Study Design: Choose a cross-sectional or longitudinal study design to assess the impact of refractive errors. Longitudinal studies could provide insights into changes over time.

Participant Selection: Randomly select a representative sample of school students. Ensure a diverse demographic representation to enhance the generalizability of the findings.

Informed Consent: Obtain informed consent from participants, explaining the purpose, procedures, and potential risks and benefits of the study.

Data Collection: Utilize a combination of quantitative and qualitative methods. Conduct vision screenings, distribute questionnaires to assess academic performance, quality of life, and mental health. Also, conduct interviews or focus group discussions to gather qualitative insights.

Clinical Assessments: Include clinical assessments of refractive errors using optometric tools. Collaborate with eye care professionals for accurate diagnosis. Firstly, vision should be checked and refraction should be done. We will used Snellen's acuity chart, trial frame, chair, occluder, pinhole to take vision. Then, torchlight will be focused on the anterior chamber.

The students those who had visual acuity less than 6/6 in either eye was examined again by putting the pinhole were examined aging by putting the pinhole in front of each eye for any improvement on the Snellen chart, were included in this study. And students who had visual acuity 6/6 were excluded from the study.

Questionnaires: Develop standardized questionnaires assessing academic performance, quality of life, and mental health. Ensure questions are clear and relevant to the study objectives.

Sampling Technique: In this study total 162 students were taken, those who had less than 6/6 vision. Research on the effects of refractive errors involves collecting samples to study how vision abnormalities like myopia, hypermetropia, and astigmatism impact individuals. Random selection of participants from various schools within the specified age range.

RESULTS

Total 162 school students were randomly selected for this study. A questionnaires sheet was supplied to all the school students, which was included the visual performance, clinical examination, where 91 (56.17%) were girls and 71 (43.83%) were boys [Table No. 1].

Table No – 1 Gender wise students' distribution

Gender	Students	%
Boys	71	43.83%
Girls	91	56.17%
Total	162	100.00%

Out of 162 school students, 71 were boys, where 44 (27.16%) students were suffering headache and 27 (16.67%) students had no headache problems. Again, out of total 91 girls' students, 62 (38.27%) girls were suffering headache and 29 (17.90%) girls' students had no headache [Table No. 2].

Table no – 2 Gender wise headache sufferer

Gender	Headache	Students	%
Boys	Yes	44	27.16%
	No	27	16.67%
Girls	Yes	62	38.27%
	No	29	17.90%
Total		162	100.00%

Total 162 school students were involved in this study, out of 71 boys, 53 (32.72%) male students have had blurred vision and 18 (11.11%) students had no blurred vision problems; again, out of total 91 female students, 77 (47.53%) girls' students have had blurred vision and 14 (8.64%) students had no blurred vision [Table No. 3].

Table no – 3 Gender wise Blurred Vision sufferer

Gender	Blurred Vision	Students	%
Boys	Yes	53	32.72%
	No	18	11.11%
Girls	Yes	77	47.53%
	No	14	8.64%
Total		162	100.00%

Total 162 school students were involved in this study, out of 71 boys, 39 (24.07%) male students have had watering and 32 (19.75%) students had no watering problems; again, out of total 91 female students, 41 (25.31%) girls' students have had watering and 50 (30.86%) students had no watering. [Table No. 4].

Table no – 4 Gender wise watering sufferer

Gender	Watering	Students	%
Boys	Yes	39	24.07%
	No	32	19.75%
Girls	Yes	41	25.31%
	No	50	30.86%
Total		162	100.00%

Total 162 school students were involved in this study, out of 71 boys, 37 (22.84%) male students have had myopic, 13 (8.02%) students had hypermetropic and 21 (12.96%) students were astigmatic; again, out of total 91 female students, 51 (31.48%) girls' students have had myopic, and 17 (10.49%) students had hypermetropic and 23 (14.20%) students were astigmatic. [Table No. 5]

Table – 5 Gender wise refractive errors distributions

Refractive errors	Boys	%	Girls	%	Total
Myopia	37	22.84%	51	31.48%	88 (54.32%)
Hypermetropia	13	8.02%	17	10.49%	20 (12.35%)
Astigmatism	21	12.96%	23	14.20%	44 (27.16%)
Total	71	43.83%	91	56.17%	162 (100.00%)

Total 162 school students were affected in study due their refractive errors. In this study we were divided into three groups by which the students hampered their study life among boys' and girls' students. Out of 71 boys, 23 (22.84%) male students were reducing their study time less than 2 hours, 34 (8.02%) students were reducing their study time less than 3 hours and 14 (8.64%) students were reducing their study time more than 3 hours; again, out of total 91 female students, 21 (12.96%) male students were reducing their study time less than 2 hours, 52 (32.10%) students were reducing their study time less than 3 hours and 18 (11.11%) students were reducing their study time more than 3 hours. [Table No. 6]

Table – 6 Gender wise reducing study time due to refractive errors

Reducing study time	Boys	%	Girls	%	Total
Less than 2 hours	23	14.20%	21	12.96%	44 (27.16%)
Less than 3 hours	34	20.99%	52	32.10%	86 (53.09%)
More than 3 hours	14	8.64%	18	11.11%	32 (19.75%)
Total	71	43.83%	91	56.17%	162 (100.00%)

DISCUSSION

In the above survey a clear picture was found of visual effects among the secondary school students. In this study total 162 secondary school students were randomly examined, which includes the visual performance were 56.17% girls and 43.83% were boys. These students were suffering from different types of refractive error.

In this study, around 62 (38.27%) students were girls and 44 (27.16%) students were boys suffered from headache; 77 (47.53%) girls and 53 (32.72%) boys were suffered from blurred vision; 39 (24.07%) students were girls and 39 (24.07%) students were boys suffered from watering.

In this study, we also found that the complications like headache and blurring of vision due to refractive error, among secondary school students, female students were more than male students.

The prevalence of refractive errors was; 37 (22.84%) male students were myopic, 13 (8.02%) students were hypermetropic and 21 (12.96%) students were astigmatic; again, 51 (31.48%) girls' students were myopic, and 17 (10.49%) students were hypermetropic and 23 (14.20%) students were astigmatic.

It was also found that, due to refractive errors students were reducing their study time, that's directly hampered their study life. So, early detection or refractive errors correction is the most essentials for secondary school students.

The more indulgence in the study is one of major reason to have refractive error whether it is through computer or any digital media or else by reading books for a prolong hour. Hence, according to the discussions, long duration of studies is affecting the ocular health among.

CONCLUSION

The study can be concluded, effect of refractive error among secondary school student. It is very important to make sure that, the eyes must be checked very often by any optometrist or ophthalmologist at least once in a month to be aware of the leading symptoms effecting the ocular health by creating further complications and destroying the interest in studies and many other activities.

If refractive errors is uncorrected or untreated then what complication occurs in the eye; uncorrected refractive error is the most common cause of vision impairment, and the second leading cause of blindness in the world. During early childhood, uncorrected refractive errors may affect visual development and result in amblyopia. The largest burden of refractive error is myopia which significantly increases the risk of blinding conditions such as myopic macular degeneration, glaucoma, and cataract. It can even result in a permanent and uncorrected degradation in vision called refractive amblyopia. in adult, having blurry vision can be uncomfortable, inconvenient, and even unsafe, especially while driving or operating machinery. Uncorrected refractive errors are the main cause of visual impairment. According to the WORLD HEALTH ORGANIZATION, an estimated 153 million people live with visual impairment due to uncorrected refractive errors. There are a few simple solutions that are available to correct refractive error, including eyeglasses, contact lens, or different kinds of surgery. Eyeglasses are the most common and simple solution. An eye care professional can measure you for a pair of eyeglasses for effective correction. They can be permanently treated with LASIK and other vision correction surgery.

REFERENCES

1. S.K. BASAK'S ESSENTIAL BOOK OF OPHTHALMOLOGY.
2. A.K. KHURANA ESSENTIAL OF OPHTHALMOLOGY.
3. https://scholar.Google.com/?hl=en&as_sdt=0%2c5&q=+Impacts+of+refractive+errorG=#d=gs_qabs&t=1709057128446&u=%23p%3Dn6JMZtBwcqoj
4. <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/1937488/>
5. https://www.ijhsr.org/IJHSR_Vol.12_iIssue.&_July2022/ILHSR43.pdf
6. <https://www.loulingglassoptical.com/important/eye/health/when/it/comes/to/stydying/>
7. <https://globalnews.ca/news/4257827//what/cause/refractiveerror>
8. <http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC2040246>